

ON CHLORALAMIDES. THE REACTION OF POTASSIUM
CYANIDE ON α -CHLOROCHLORAL-CHLORO-2-METHOXY-
AND α -CHLOROCHLORAL-BROMO-2-METHOXYBENZ-
AMIDES AND THE HYDROLYSIS OF THE
RESULTING α -CYANO COMPOUNDS.

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α -Chlorochloral-chloro-2-methoxy- and α -chlorochloral-bromo-2-methoxybenzamides have been reacted with potassium cyanide to obtain α -cyano compounds of the type $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot C(CN) : CCl_2$. The nitriles have been hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to the corresponding carboxylic acids which have formed metallic salts.

To extend the authors' previous investigations (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 677), the reaction of potassium cyanide has been tried on α -chlorochloral-chloro-2-methoxy- and α -chlorochloral-bromo-2-methoxybenzamides $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot CH(Cl) \cdot CCl_2$. The α -chlorine atom, being very reactive, better regulates the cyanide reaction than does the α -hydroxyl group, which as in chloral-acetamide and chloral-benzamide, leads to complex substances of unknown constitution (Schiff and Speciale, *Gazzetta*, 1879, **9**, 335). By using an excess of potassium cyanide in dry acetone medium, α -cyano compounds have been isolated, which, however, are not the simple substitution products $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot CH(CN) \cdot CCl_2$. It is found that potassium cyanide, besides substituting the α -chlorine atom, simultaneously removes a molecule of hydrogen chloride from the chloralamide group, giving rise to a $\beta\beta$ -dichloro- α -cyanovinyl derivative $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot C(CN) : CCl_2$.

The spontaneous formation of unsaturation explains the need for ^{an} excess of potassium cyanide in the reaction. Chloral condensation compounds, $R'CH(OH) \cdot CCl_2$, have long been known to yield dichlorovinyl derivatives by the action of alcoholic potash (*cf.* Goldschmidt, *Ber.*, 1873, **6**, 985), potassium cyanide here also acting like alkali.

The nitriles have been hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to the corresponding carboxylic acids, $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot C(COOH) : CCl_2$.

The yield of cyano compounds is rather poor (*ca* 39%), but their conversion into acids is quantitative. The acids are comparatively unstable and tend to decompose on melting (or heating with alkalis) with evolution of gas.

Although the above compounds are unsaturated, they do not add bromine due to the resisting polar effects of the adjacent radicals (*cf.* Hugo and Bauer, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3317; Ley, *ibid.*, 1917, 50, 243).

Hirwe and Deshpande (*private communication*) have obtained analogous, unsaturated products, while studying the reaction of potassium cyanide on α -chlorochloral-tolylamides.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Potassium Cyanide Reaction.—Potassium cyanide (5 g.) was added to a dry acetone solution of the freshly prepared α -chlorochloral-amide (5 g.) in a bottle fitted with a spring stopper, with cooling and then the mixture was mechanically shaken for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, during which period a rapid colour change (usually from pinkish to rusty-red to brown) was observed. Shortly after this change of colour ceased the reaction mixture was poured into ice-water, when the α -cyano compound was precipitated.

Hydrolysis of the α -Cyano Compound.—The α -cyano compound (2 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) were mixed together in a tube and heated under reflux on a steam-bath for about 2 hours, the mixture being well shaken from time to time. The solid, without going into solution, slowly changed into a flocculent mass. It was filtered off after cooling, washed and then dissolved in a solution of sodium carbonate and filtered. The carboxylic acid was obtained by acidification of the solution with dilute hydrochloric acid.

The sodium salt of the acid was prepared in acetone solution by neutralisation; other salts were prepared by double decomposition of the alkali or ammonium salt. The compounds described below gave no ferric reaction.

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared from α -chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide, is soluble readily in methanol, alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid and sparingly in chloroform and benzene. It crystallised from acetone in long, shining needles, m.p. 171-72°. yield 2 g. (Found: C, 43.35; H, 2.20; N, 9.0; Cl, 35.0. $C_{11}H_7O_2N_2Cl_3$ requires C, 43.21; H, 2.29; N, 9.17; Cl, 34.86 per cent).

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -carboxyvinyl-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared from $\beta\beta$ -dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide, is soluble readily in methanol, alcohol, acetone and sparingly in glacial acetic acid. It crystallised from acetone in white, shining needles m.p. 199-200° (decomp.) It turned pinkish on long standing. (Found: N, 4.17; Cl, 32.73; Equiv., 325.7. $C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_3$ requires N, 4.31; Cl, 32.83 per cent. Equiv., 324.5).

The *sodium salt* crystallised from water in pinkish needles. (Found: Na, 6'8p. $C_{11}H_7O_4NCl_3Na$ requires Na, 6'64 per cent).

The *barium salt* crystallised from water in white needles which became pinkish on standing. [Found: Ba, 17.0; H_2O , 4'5r. $(C_{11}H_7O_4NCl_3)_2Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 16'75; H_2O , 4'39 per cent].

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-3:5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide was prepared from α -chlorochloral-3:5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide. It is soluble in methanol, alcohol, acetone and glacial acetic acid and crystallises from acetone in long, shining needles, m.p. 172-73°, yield 1'8 g. (Found: N, 8'93; Cl, 42'04. $C_{11}H_6O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires N, 8'42; Cl, 41'77 per cent).

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -carboxyvinyl-3:5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared from $\beta\beta$ -dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-3:5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide, crystallised from acetone in long, shining needles, m.p. 202-3° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 39.33; Equiv., 358'i. $C_{11}H_7O_4NCl_4$ requires Cl, 39'56 per cent. Equiv., 358'9).

The *sodium salt* crystallised from water in pinkish needles. (Found: Na, 5'40; H_2O , 4.31. $C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_4Na, H_2O$ requires Na, 5'76; H_2O , 4'5r per cent).

The *barium salt* crystallised from water in greenish yellow, thick plates. [Found: Ba, 15'19, 15'16. $(C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_4)_2Ba, 4H_2O$ requires Ba, 14'85 per cent].

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-5-bromo-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared from α -chlorochloral-5-bromo-2-methoxybenzamide, crystallised from acetone in long shining needles, m.p. 177-78°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 8'02; Halogen, 42'99. $C_{11}H_7O_2N_2Cl_2Br$ requires N, 8'0; Halogen, 43'09 per cent).

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -carboxyvinyl-5-bromo-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared from $\beta\beta$ -dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-5-bromo-2-methoxybenzamide, crystallised from acetone in shining needles, m.p. 203-4° (decomp.). (Found: N, 3'70; Halogen, 40'82; Equiv., 368.5. $C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_2Br$ requires N, 3'79; Halogen, 40'87 per cent. Equiv., 368.9).

The *sodium salt* crystallised from water in needles. (Found: Na, 5'54. $C_{11}H_7O_4NCl_2BrNa$ requires Na, 5'88 per cent).

The *calcium salt* crystallised from water in plates. [Found: Ca, 5'10, 4.98. $(C_{11}H_7O_4NCl_2Br)_2Ca, 2H_2O$ requires Ca, 4'93 per cent].

$\beta\beta$ -Dichloro- α -cyanovinyl-3:5-dibromo-2-methoxybenzamide was prepared from α -chlorochloral-3:5-dibromo-2-methoxybenzamide. It crystallised from acetone in long shining needles, m.p. 220-21° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: N, 6'62; Halogen, 54'00. $C_{11}H_6O_2N_2Cl_2Br_2$ requires N, 6'53; Halogen, 53'83 per cent).

ββ-Dichloro-*α*-carboxyvinyl-3:5-dibromo-2-methoxybenzamide was prepared from *ββ*-dichloro-*α*-cyanovinyl-3:5-dibromo-2-methoxybenzamide. It crystallised from acetone in shining needles, m p. 217-18° (decomp.) It turned brownish on standing. (Found: Halogen, 51.36; Equiv., 447.3. $C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_2Br_2$ requires Halogen, 51.53 per cent. Equiv., 447.8).

The *sodium salt* crystallised from water in needles. (Found: Na, 4.38; H_2O , 7.40. $C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_2Br_2Na$, $2H_2O$ requires Na, 4.54; H_2O , 7.11 per cent).

The *barium salt* crystallised from water in plates. [Found: Ba, 12.92, 12.94. $(C_{11}H_6O_4NCl_2Br_2)_2Ba$, $3H_2O$ requires Ba, 12.66 per cent].

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